

Outcome of Conservative Management of Large Periapical Cyst Like lesion using a Bioceramic Material - A Case Report

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Abstract

A periapical cyst (Radicular cyst) is most common odontogenic cyst of oral cavity which arises from epithelial remnants which form by an inflammatory process originating from pulpal necrosis of a nonvital tooth. This cyst associated with non-vital tooth and generally visible on radiographs. Radiographic interpretation of the lesion is a round or oval, well-circumscribed radiolucency involving the apex of the tooth. A 12 year-old female patient reported to department of with chief complain pus discharge, swelling and mobility of teeth in upper front region of jaw since 3 months Clinical and radiological findings were suggestive of periapical radicular cyst. Nonsurgical endodontic therapy was performed using 5% sodium hypochlorite, 2% chlorhexidine and normal saline and Calcium hydroxide intra canal medicament and MTA obturation. A 12 months follow-up radiographic examination revealed progressive involution of periapical radiolucency without any clinical symptoms. Periapical cysts respond favourably to non-surgical endodontic treatment.

Keywords: Non-surgical endodontic therapy, apical cyst, periapical cyst, radicular cyst, periapical lesion

Introduction

A periapical cyst (radicular cyst) is generally defined as a cyst arising from epithelial residues (cell rests of Malassez) in the periodontal ligament as a consequence of inflammation, usually following the death of the dental pulp. These cysts are the most common odontogenic cystic lesions of inflammatory origin affecting the jaws. They are most commonly found at the apices of the involved teeth; however, they may accessory root canals. Periapical cyst(Radicular cysts)areassociated with non-vital tooth typically apparent on radiographs¹. Over time, this cyst either stays the same size or gets bigger. The most commonly involved teeth are maxillary anterior followed by premolars and molars. The prevalence of periapical cysts varies between 8.7% and 37.7% of chronic inflammatory periapical lesions². Most radicular cysts appear as round- or pear-shaped, unilocular, lucent lesions in the periapical region. They are usually <1 cm in diameter and are bordered by a thin rim of cortical bone. Cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) may provide a more accurate diagnosis than biopsy in differentiating cyst from granuloma.

Case Report

A 12-year female patient reported to the Department of Pedodontics and Preventive Dentistry, Career Post Graduate Institute of Dental Sciences and Hospital, Lucknow, with a complaint of pus discharge, swelling and mobility of teeth in upper front region of jaw since 3 months. There is no relevant past dental history or medical history found. Clinical examination revealed that maxillary left central incisor (21) and left lateral (22) were found to be non-vital after pulp vitality test with grade II mobility of left central incisor. Soft tissue examination revealed sinus opening with vestibular tenderness in relation to tooth 22.

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Figure1: Preoperative clinical photograph and intraoral periapical Radiograph

Intraoral periapical radiograph shows well defined radiolucency of considerable size w.r.t 21 and 22. The radiographic lesion size were suggestive of chronic periapical abscess in relation with 21 and 22. Further investigation like CBCT showed that A well defined unilocular radiolucency seen at apical portion of tooth i.r.t 21 and 22 (19.2mmx 12.1 mmx23.6mm) (Superoinferiorlyx Buccopa-latally x Mesiodistally) with an area of 295.5 mm² . Buccal cortex, palatal cortex, nasal floor and incisive foramen are perforated. Based on history,clinical examination and radiographic examination a final diagnosis of infected periapical cyst i.r.t left maxillary central incisor (21) and lateral incisor (22) was made and the treatment plan was formulated to manage the case through conservative nonsurgical approach.

Figure 2: Pre-operative CBCT Image - 3D View

Since tooth was non-vital, access opening was done i.r.t 21 and 22 without local anaesthesia and the necrotic pulp tissue was extirpated followed by copious irrigation with 5% sodium hypochloride, 2% chlorhexidine and normal saline. Following 3 days of access opening swelling was subsided and biomechanical preparation (i.e. cleaning and shaping of canals) was done by pro taper gold heat activated files (SuperEndo, India) followed by copious irrigation. Temporary intracanal medicament Ca(OH)₂ dressing was given to the patient and cavity was sealed with temporary dressing. 1 week later, Ca(OH)₂ dressing was removed and after proper irrigation and drying of canal, Metapex (META Bio Med, Korea) dressing was given. After 3 months of recall,

teeth 21,22 were obturated with MTA (BioStructure SafeEndo, India) and were restored with composite. After regular follow-up of 3 months interval till 1 year, there was reduction in size of the lesion in periapical radiograph. After 1 year of follow-up CBCT examination was done to see the healing of the lesion.

The CBCT showed a well defined radiolucency with noncorticated borders seen at apical portion of tooth i.r.t 21 and 22 (6.4mm x 6.6mm x 5.1mm) (Superoinferiorly x Buccopalatally x Mesiodistally) with an area of 18.7 mm².

Figure 3: Post-operative CBCT Image after 12 Months Follow up

Discussion

A large periapical cyst lesion shows complete healing and regression of lesion after non surgical endodontic therapy because of decrease in periapical inflammation via reduced inflammatory mediators, proinflammatory cytokines, with growth factors released by innate and adaptive immune cells and the epithelial cells of a cyst lining epithelium will die of apoptosis³. In the present case, the infected periapical cyst (radicular cyst) was chosen for conservative non surgical management approach as the patient was very young, would cause less psychological trauma and prognosis of tooth 21 was not good.

The success of nonsurgical endodontic treatment method is based on appropriate cleaning and disinfection of the root canal. Calcium hydroxide, historically, is widely used as an intracanal endodontic material, due to its high alkaline nature, tissue dissolving effect, causes induction of repair by hard tissue formation and has bactericidal effect but will remain in the tissue for considerable time and therefore cannot be considered biocompatible^{4,5}. Its antibacterial actions are due to its effect on bacterial cytoplasmic membranes, protein denaturation, destruction to DNA, action on lipopolysaccharides etc.

Metapex, a silicone oil based calcium hydroxide paste containing 38% of the iodoform is a well known intracanal dressing. It contains silicone oil as a vehicle and has a pH below that which is said to be effective in killing *Enterococcus faecalis*. Oily vehicles are said to increase the

antimicrobial effects of calcium hydroxide against *Enterococcus faecalis* and other bacteria.⁶ The antimicrobial effects of calcium hydroxide is related to its high pH of 12.5 which is said to have a destructive effect on the cell membranes and protein structures. In the present case the teeth 21, 22 were obturated with MTA because of its dynamic properties like its minimal cytotoxicity, promotion of hard tissue induction in the periodontal tissues, stimulation of dentin bridge formation adjacent to dental pulp and superior sealing capability⁷. MTA is capable of activation of cementoblasts. It allows for overgrowth of cementum and also facilitates regeneration of PDL⁸. Budding (2008) found that the set MTA when exposed to water it releases calcium hydroxide which might be responsible for its cementogenesis property⁹.

Conclusion

Management of periapical cyst is dependent on various aspect like size of lesion, physical health of individual, age of individual, mental health of individual¹⁰. The clinical case report presented in this article was managed successfully by endodontic therapy with emphasis on thorough debridement, disinfection and obturation of the root canal system. However, in specific situations where the size and extent of the lesion is of critical importance, surgical management is a viable option.

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